

Deep water

CR1002 — a promising rice cultivar for rainfed waterlogged conditions

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CR1002 is a new rice strain derived from a cross of CR70 and Pankaj, made at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. It was included in a yield trial of 20 long-growth-duration rices in West Bengal under rainfed, ill-drained conditions in 1978 kharif. An unprecedented flood submerged all entries.

The experiment was in randomized

Yield and performance of the different strains exposed to severe flooding. West Bengal, India, 1978.

Designation	Growth duration (days)	yield (t/ha)
CR1002	154	3.5
IET5656	160	1.8
CO38	156	1.5
IR34	158	1.3
Pankaj (control)	166	1.3
IR4219-35-3-3	173	1.3
IET3257	160	1.0
CR1009	172	1.0
CR1006	184	0.5
CR1011	173	0.4
IET5633	173	0.0

block design with four replications. Fertilizer was applied at 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. At 46 days after transplanting the experimental plot was completely submerged for 4 days. The water remained at a depth of 75 to 55 cm for 10 more days. CR1002 had 10% dead tillers and IR4219-35-3-3, 66%. Other entries had from 75 to 98% dead tillers.

The severe flood stunted the plants and delayed their maturity (see table). CR1002 yielded highest — 3.5 t/ha — followed by IET5656.

Such flash floods are common in kharif in low-lying areas in West Bengal and other parts of India. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Seed transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*

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The survival of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, the causal agent of leaf scald disease of rice, was studied in the laboratory using the standard agar plating and blotter methods of detection. Seeds of the susceptible breeding line IR1487-372-1-1 were collected from a naturally infested field, stored at four temperatures (20, 25, 30, and 35°C), and examined periodically for the presence of the pathogen.

The presence of *R. oryzae* on seeds was detected through seed plating on potato-dextrose-agar medium (PDA), and the blotter test. The blotter test detected higher infestation than the plating method did after 14 weeks of seed storage. The highest recorded rate of infested seeds was 90% for the blotter test and 47.5% for plating (see table).

The pathogen survived as long as

Percentages of seeds infested with *Rhynchosporium oryzae* at storage temperatures of 20, 25, 30, and 35°C, as determined by the blotter and plating methods.

Weeks in storage	Seed infestation ^a (%) at							
	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C	
	AD	SD	AD	SD	AD	SD	AD	SD
	<i>Blotter method</i>							
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	30.0	0
6	20.0	40.0	20.0	40.0	20.0	20.0	50.0	10.0
8	20.0	0	10.0	10.0	60.0	80.0	10.0	10.0
10	10.0	10.0	10.0	0	40.0	50.0	60.0	50.0
12	10.0	40.0	10.0	10.0	30.0	70.0	80.0	40.0
14	40.0	50.0	30.0	0	70.0	30.0	40.0	30.0
16	70.0	80.0	30.0	40.0	60.0	70.0	60.0	70.0
20	20.0	40.0	50.0	40.0	70.0	50.0	50.0	50.0
24	70.0	50.0	40.0	10.0	70.0	60.0	40.0	80.0
28	30.0	90.0	40.0	60.0	70.0	90.0	60.0	60.0
	<i>Plating method</i>							
2	2.5	47.5	22.5	17.5	32.5	27.5	32.5	30.0
6	15.0	35.0	17.0	15.0	30.0	22.5	30.0	30.0
8	27.5	30.0	25.0	40.0	30.0	40.0	27.5	42.5
10	32.5	25.0	22.5	27.5	20.0	27.5	22.5	20.0
14	15.0	17.5	10.0	10.0	17.5	32.5	30.0	30.0
16	15.0	20.0	17.5	22.5	10.0	30.0	25.0	2.5
20	35.0	27.5	30.0	15.0	35.0	27.5	32.5	30.0
24	21.5	42.5	25.0	30.0	12.5	15.0	20.0	21.5
28	35.0	27.5	30.0	20.0	22.5	25.0	22.5	37.5

^aAD = air-dried, SD = sun-dried.

7 months at all of the storage temperatures in both air- and sun-dried

samples. The high percentage of transmissibility and the length of survival

time in the grains indicated that *R. oryzae* is a seedborne pathogen and that infested seeds may serve as a primary source of inoculum.

R. oryzae usually grew over or dominated other associated organisms on

PDA. Sometimes it grew in mixed culture with other fast-growing fungi, or formed distinct individual colonies side by side with colonies of other organisms. Other fungal species that were commonly encountered during the study, in the

order of their frequency of isolation, were *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Nigrospora*, *Helminthosporium*, *Phoma*, *Cercospora*, and other unidentified and non-sporulating fungi. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in China

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In March 1979, the senior author found in 3 lines of hybrid rice about 60 hills infected by a disease in an experimental plot in Zhonghwa country, Guangdong, PROC. The diseased plants were stunted and their leaves were green but ragged and twisted.

The diseased hills were transplanted in pots and kept at GAAS. At later growth stages, their flag leaves were short, distorted, and occasionally ragged. Numerous nodal panicles were produced but many were incompletely exerted and most of the grains were empty (see figure). A few swollen veins were found on the lower surface of leaf blades and the outer surface of leaf sheaths. All the symptoms were similar to those of rice ragged stunt disease in the Philippines.

Brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* were confined on diseased plants for acquisition feeding. The viruliferous

A rice hill infected with ragged stunt disease in China.

insects were then used to inoculate healthy seedlings, which then developed the above-mentioned symptoms, indicating that brown planthoppers could transmit the disease.

The results identify the symptoms of the disease found in Zhonghwa as those of rice ragged stunt in the Philippines. This may be the first record of ragged stunt in China. ■

Effectiveness of fungicides in the control of blast (neck rot)

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No suitable chemicals to control blast (neck rot) infection caused by *Piricularia oryzae* has been reported in Uttar Pradesh. Therefore the relative effectiveness of some fungicides was tested in the field.

Foliar sprays of four fungicides — edifenphos, Miltox, blue copper, and

Relative effectiveness of some fungicides on blast (neck rot) incidence and grain yield of paddy during kharif seasons of 1974–75 and 1975–76.

Fungicide	Dose (% active ingredient)	Blast (neck rot) incidence (%) (mean of 4 replicates)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1974–75	1975–76	1974–75	1975–76
Edifenphos	0.1	2.1	2.8	3.3	3.4
Miltox	0.25	4.3	5.4	3.0	2.9
Blue copper	0.30	7.0	6.0	2.7	2.2
Kitazin 17%	988 kg/ha	10.0	8.6	2.1	1.9
Control	—	12.6	10.3	1.7	1.4
C.D. @5% (critical deviation)				2.20	4.25

Kitazin—were tested on the susceptible variety Basmati 370 in a randomized

block design. Fertilizer was applied at 80 kg N/ha. Spraying was done 25, 35,